

THE DEVELOPMENT OF AQUAEXPLORERS MODULE FOR SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN PENANG: A PILOT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background Although an aquatic activities such as swimming and hydro therapy is a common activities in Special Education classes in Penang, there are no one specific module that can be used as a guidance for that activities which contributed to an activity without objectives and goals **Aims** This study aimed to discover the effect of Aquaexplorers Module implementation on the knowledge and self-confidence of Special Education Teachers in Penang. The limitations of this study is to test this module during a pandemic. **Methodology** 17 Special Education (Learning Disability) teachers in Penang participated in a three day course on Aquaexplorers Module implementation. A pre-test consist of a questionnaire was given before the course begin to see the baseline of the teachers current knowledge and confidence in handling water activities and a post-test using same questionnaire was given after the course ended. The questionnaire is validated by Cohen Kappa validation test. **Result** A Chi Square test showed that the level of knowledge and confidence of the Special Education teachers in the post-test were significantly increased (M= 46.11, SD = 3.230) after the implementation of Aquaexplorers module compared to the pre-test score (M= 33.11, SD = 2.208). Simplified yet more suitable instructions, objectives and activities in a module can be used to improve the Special Education teachers knowledge and confidence in handling water activities. Future research can focus on improving the of Aquaexplorers Module for Special Education Teachers based on the suggestion from this pilot study.

Keywords: Special Education; teachers, aquatic activities, modules, knowledge, confidence

1. Introduction

Pupils with special needs (learning disabilities) are often associated with psychological and neurological difficulties against language response either oral, written, cognitive perception or psychomotor activity. Pupils with special needs (learning disabilities) are actually unable to follow classes using the syllabus and pedagogical ways for normal children in the mainstream classes (Ali & Sahal, 2016). This is due to the difference approach needed for them compared

to the ordinary children. Physically, special needs (learning disability) students do not have any physical, emotional, vision, hearing or mental disabilities and this is the main reason why most people cannot identify them and treated them the same as the students in the mainstream. However, there are ways to identify these children, one of which is to know their unique features. Among the features that are easy to identify are unsatisfactory academic achievement, weak in mathematical and language subjects and also do not show interest in the classroom (Ali & Sahal, 2016). It is observed that they are also only able to focus on teaching and learning activities in a short period, are often drowsy, easily distracted and always embarrassed to ask questions in the classroom even if they do not understand (Ali & Sahal, 2016). Due to these factors, special needs students are usually left out in the main stream classes. As a special education teacher, we should know these factors in order to identify the appropriate teaching and learning delivery method for these special needs (learning disability) students.

The Special Education Integration Program (PPKI) has varieties of interesting and appropriate pedagogical techniques for special needs (learning disability) students and among them is the Classroom External Learning (PLBD) which includes various activities such as study tours and field activities such as water activities. The objective of the PLBD's programme is to prepare students to learn through the concept of teaching, learning and assessment process. Classroom External Learning (PLBD) consists of three domains which are knowledge, attitude and skills (Sulaiman et al., 2011). Classroom External Learning (PLBD) also enables students to think and master knowledge through contextual experience, enhance interest and attitude of students to learn and apply pure values and socialization in themselves.

Confident is a word derived from a Latin word "Confider" which means "to trust" while self-confidence means to have trust and faith in ourselves, believe in our ability in performing some tasks (Kharani, 2019). As a Special Education teacher, to have confidence in handling special needs students is very important in ensuring quality learning and to boost the student confidence optimally. Past research show that teachers gain their confidence through expansions in professional field by acquisition of knowledge and skills, participation in networks of collaborative learning communities and the ability to exercise professional teaching (Nolan & Molla, 2017). Thus, the teacher confidence can be boost through their engagement with students based on experience, gain knowledge for their teaching skills and participate in a course with the fellow teachers. In a study related to handling challenging behaviour of special education students, the data analysis showed that teachers with less experience teaching special needs students have the least confidence in managing the challenging behaviors of the special needs students with only 44% contribution in this matter (Byrd & Alexander, 2020). The more interesting finding is, 90% of the participants reported that experience was the biggest contributor to their confidence in managing challenging behaviors (Byrd & Alexander, 2020). This result proved that individuals without experience handling special needs students will have problems handling water activities for the students. Teacher confidence and school type also determined to be significant predictors for the self-efficacy of teachers in handling special needs students (Chao et.al; 2017).

1.1 Water Activities in Special Education Classes

Classroom External Learning (PLBD) consists of three models which are PLBD model 1,2 and 3. PLBD model 1 is conducted outside the classroom within the school area such as in the computer labs, Science Laboratory and Herbal Park. The PLBD 2 model is PLBD conducted near the school area such as the village area, outside the school fence and nearby housing

estate. The PLBD 3 model is often conducted away from school areas such as in public libraries, fire stations and swimming pools. Water activities in the PLBD programme is an activities conducted by the Special Education Integration Program (PPKI) throughout Malaysia using the PLBD 3 module involving a swimming pool and the programme has become one of the routine activities for PPKI classes. However, water activities carried out by the Special Education Integration Program (PPKI) have no plans in its implementation, no written objective, no trained teachers and no standardized guide to execute the programme.

1.2 Shortcoming in Penang PPKI Water Activities

In the Classroom External Learning (PLBD) among Special Education Integration Program (PPKI) in Penang, aquatic or water activities are often carried out by playing in the swimming pool conducted by outsiders who have a water safety and rescue certificate such as the Malaysian Public Service Agency (APAM) or the Fire Brigaders. These people has no skills in handling special needs students (learning disability) and the school has to pay them according to hours at an expensive rate (Jabatan Pendidikan Negeri Pulau Pinang, 2018). This is the obstacles in handling water activity for the special needs students (learning disability) in Malaysia, specifically in Penang even though it has a very significant positive impact to the special needs students (learning disability). Often being carried out without goals, direction and guidance is actually a result of no exposure and training to the teachers in carrying out these water activities.

The skills of the Penang Special Education Teacher in the field of water activities are also at a very low level where the results of the survey found that only 4 people from 616 specialized education teachers in Penang had the basic skills of swimming and able to handle water activities while 0 out of 616 special integration education teachers in Penang had a certificate of lifesaving and water rescue (Jabatan Pendidikan Negeri Pulau Pinang, 2018). This is a big risk taken by the school as 56% of these special integration education program has conducted water activities at least once every year with no teacher with expertise nor qualification handling it (Jabatan Pendidikan Negeri Pulau Pinang, 2018). Swimming activities are also conducted without any objectives, guidelines or specific modules for the performance improvement of special needs students (learning disability) through this activity (Jabatan Pendidikan Negeri Pulau Pinang, 2018). This has caused most teachers to carry out swimming activities just by playing water without any objective for specific performance improvements.

Swimming modules for special needs students are not widely published (Kraft et al., 2019) while water activities for special needs (learning disability) students have been carried out for a long time in the Special Education Integration Program (PPKI). This situation had led to an issue among the teachers, administrators and parents where this water activities was often questioned by parents and school administration as there were no significant results that can be proved through this activity and no guide nor module used throughout the activity to prove that this activity was actually objective, aimed and can be operated by special educational teachers well and safely.

Handling water activities actually requires high skills especially when it involves special needs students. Handling these activities without expertise or disclosure in how to operate and overcome risks factors will invite hazards to the teachers as well as the special needs students. Water activities executed based on a well develop modules is an essence to enhance the skills

of special needs (learning disability) students and it should also be conducted regularly in accordance with the module to ensure that the activities have a positive direction and fruitful, not just playing in the swimming pool. Teaching using modules to develop curriculum will result in more quality and productive learning (Shariza, 2017). Therefore, in order to improve the quality of teacher's teaching and student's learning in water activities through PLBD, a module development would be a very relevant move.

2. Aquaexplorers Module for Special Education Teachers-The Pilot Study

As a Special Education Teacher, to have knowledge and self-confidence in their field is crucial. The basis for effective teaching in special education is by giving instructions and support to special needs students based on the teacher's professional evaluation and their high knowledge of individual needs (McLeskey, 2017). Knowledge is an abstract and a powerful concept leading to development, but the true definition of the word is still fuzzy (Bolisani & Bratianu, 2018). Wikipedia define knowledge as a skill or expertise that a person may have gained either by experience or through education (Carayannis & Campbell, 2019). Nowadays, numerous publications has proven that knowledge has become increasingly important for society, economy, and also democracy (Carayannis & Campbell, 2019). That means knowledge is very important in so many field. In the context of Special Education, teachers appeared to be most knowledgeable and more frequently to implement certain skills based on their own knowledge and expertise. Teachers' also believe that their knowledge in certain area was correlated with their decision of choosing strategies in teaching or delivering new skills (Moore et.al, 2017). Past research also suggest that teacher education and professional development programs can be use in improving the teacher's skills and knowledge (Byrd & Alexander, 2020). Specific training and experience had a significant influence on the knowledge in handling special educations students (Sanz-Cervera et.al, 2017). These statement shows that an appropriate module and courses for teachers can improve their ability in handling activities for the special education students (learning disability)

2.1 Various approach in Special Education

There are various approaches practice by the special education teachers and all approaches should have certain features that help the special needs students (learning disability) to continue improving their potential. Positive reinforcement such as praise and prizes is a good approach to shape the desired behavior for special needs students (learning disability) (Katmana et al., 2016). The instructions for special needs students should also focus on the contents of the instruction (Brownell et al., 2016), intensive, clear, systematic and guided by the individual (Morris et al., 2020). The approach used in delivering lesson to special needs students (learning disability)) should also be diverse and consider the capabilities and needs of individuals (Hodge et al., 2017). The approach used for them should also consider the contents of teaching, locations and teaching methods that maximize the physical involvement of activities as special needs individuals are four times more likely to suffer from diseases arising from lack of physical activity (Yun & Beamer, 2018). This shows that a modules involving physical movement are very important for this group. Among the most important things in the approach to teach the special needs students (learning disability) is the frequent repetition of each instruction and activity (Amri et al., 2019). All of these things should be emphasized in building

an approach or module to improve education for special needs students (learning disability) students.

The longitudinal study by Garcia et al., (2012) shows the results of qualitative and quantitative data derived from the study of the effectiveness of the Halliwick program on the quality of life of 674 individuals with disabilities for one year at the Institute of Medical and Rehabilitation - Das Clinicas Hospital - São Paulo University. The 10-point Halliwick model is used as the basis for the planning and learning process of water activities. The holistic 10-point Halliwick model is used in traditional swimming teaching methods and the results of this study show that after a year, this method is seen as a new way of exercising and shows that a recovery program that offers a combination of therapeutic activity and proves that recreational programs and therapies used in the Halliwick 10-point model can provide a consistent recovery to people with disabilities and also enables individuals with disabilities to achieve the maximum potential of skills and to enjoy the benefits of this program in terms of physical, psychological and social (Garcia et al; 2012).

The water activity program for disabled people has shown that the 10-point Halliwick model has dominated most of the water activity programs undertaken for the disability and revenue of this technique also shown a positive impact on various aspects in the life of the disabled. Based on this factor, the researcher has chosen this 10-point Halliwick model as the basis for the formation of Aquaexplorers Module for the use of Integration Special Education Teachers (GPKI) in handling water activities for special needs students (learning disability).

For developed countries such as Canada and the Netherlands, developing modules and swimming programs may be seen as a simple and regular practice. However, until 2019, modules and swimming programs for children with special needs are still not widely published in Canada (Kraft et al., 2019). For developing countries such as Indonesia, modules and swimming programs for children are also not widely published but there are some publications for normal children swimming program. The study by Yanto et al (2020) is a publication of the production of swimming teaching modules to increase the interest and efficiency of swimming movement techniques in children. The method used in this research is the research and development method by Borg and Gall consisting of ten steps in its construction, almost the same as the Halliwick module (Yanto et al., 2020). The collection of data for this study uses questionnaire and interviews to every user of this module which are the children who have just learned swimming and the results of the study found that there was a positive interest and response by swimmers through the use of the module (Yanto et al., 2020). In conclusion, modules formed in accordance with the needs of these users have been seen to have a positive impact on the improvement of children's swimming performance (Yanto et al., 2020) and it is possible to implement similar modules for special needs student (learning disability) in Malaysia which may provide the same positive results.

For developing countries such as Indonesia and Malaysia, the study of the development of this swimming module is not yet well-known and many published. However, for a country with many Olympic athletes such as China, the development of the swimming module according to its needs is also something new where they often use traditional swimming training modules that ignore student differences in the foundation of the swimming and prevent individual development (Chen & Xi, 2020). Studies by Chen and Xi (2020) have created four swimming modules that helped in training pupils in pool capacity, body control, basic training and integrated coordination based on teaching content, teaching techniques and assessment

systems. The reforms made by this study effectively eliminated the limitations in traditional teaching that ignores the differences in students and as well as enhancing student capabilities. The impact of teaching and forming a modular teaching technique that can be transmitted and applied by teachers and other teachers has also been developed in this study. Based on the results of this study, it is proven that a modules formed based on individual needs are able to enhance the potential of students as well as enhance the effect of teaching by the teacher (Chen & Xi, 2020). Thus, the production of swimming activity modules that consider the needs of special needs students (learning disability) are something that should also be produced and published in our country to ensure quality lessons and improve the performance of special needs students (learning disability) optimally.

The intellectual disability group is less likely to participate in physical activity despite having many studies that prove the benefits of sports for humans in general (Fiorilli et al., 2016). Individuals with disabilities such as special needs students (learning disability) are also four times more likely to suffer from illness arising from lack of physical activity (Yun & Beamer, 2018). Even with the shortage of physical activity, modules and swimming programs for special needs children are still not widely published (Kraft et al., 2019). Special Education Integration Program (PPKI) has been provided with curriculum and assessment documents (DSKP) as a learning guide, but the use of modules to develop curriculum or support existing curriculum can increase the productivity and efficiency in teaching and learning progress at school (Lunenburg, 2011). Because of this, it is clear that even though the curriculum and assessment standard documents (DSKP) have been established by the Curriculum Development Division (BPK) as a special learning guide of pupils, the use and construction of modules is still relevant and very good in learning (Pratiwi et al., 2017; Novianto et al., 2018, Nursuhud et al., 2019; Doroudi et al., 2020). Construction of modules for special needs students should also meet some of the appropriate features so that they are effective to be used. The instructions used in modules for special needs pupils should also focus on the main contents of the direction (Brownell et al., 2016), intensive, clear and systematic. The approach used in delivering teaching to special needs (learning disabilities) students should also be diverse and consider the capabilities and needs of individuals (Hodge et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2019; Morris et al., 2020). The use of modules has also been proven to have a positive impact on the knowledge of students with special needs about learning (Shariza, 2017).

The Halliwick model approach is seen to be very effective and still relevant to use until today as the basis of the swimming program for disabled people despite being created 70 years ago (Gajić et al; 2020, Gurpinar et al; 2020, Terrens et al; 2020). However, the use of this model should meet individual capabilities and needs (Hodge et al., 2017; Kraft et al., 2019; Morris et al., 2020). Water and Swimming Activities can provide benefits and various positive impacts to special needs from the Cerebral Palsi category, Autism, Down Syndrome and Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) (Hutzler et al, 1998; Pan, 2010; Jorgić et al; 2012; Fiorilli et al; 2016; Murphy & Hennebach, 2020; Silva et al; 2020; Son, 2020; Suarez et al; 2020) and the construction of the module as a guide will indeed help this process. Therefore, the construction of the module for the use of water activities in the Special Education Integration Program (PPKI) by the Integration Special Education Teachers (GPKI) for the special needs (learning disabilities) students is a necessity and its construction should be done carefully and meet their needs.

2.2 The Development of Aquaexplorers Module

Halliwick Module has 10 aspects in its application which are Mental Adjustment, Disengagement, Transversal Rotation Control, Sagittal Rotation Control, Longitudinal Rotation Control, Combined Rotation Control, Upthrust, Balance in Stillness, Turbulent Gliding, Simple Progression and Basic Swimming Movement (Vaščáková, Kudláček & Barrett, 2015).

Aquaexplorers module: Water Activity Guide for Integration Special Education Teachers contains 5 interventions containing all the above concepts that have been modified. The development process of the module has used the document analysis method (Shariza, 2017) and expert recommendation method (Poncette et al., 2020). Researcher has analyzed the standard document of curriculum and assessment of the Physical Education Special Education (Learning) for Year 1 Standard Content 1.4 - Basic Aquatic, Standard Document Curriculum and Physical Education Assessment Special Education (Learning) for Year 2 Standard Content 1.4 - Basic Aquatic, Standard Curriculum Document and Physical Education Assessment Special Education (Learning) for Year 3 Standard Content 1.5 - Basic Aquatic, Standard Document Curriculum and Physical Education Assessment Special Education (Learning) for Year 4 Standard Content 1.6 - Basic Aquatic and Content Standard 1.7 - Basic Swimming Skills, Documents Standard curriculum and assessment of Physical Education Special Education (Learning) For Year 5 Standard Content 1.7 - Basic Aquatic and Standard Document Curriculum and Physical Education Assessment Special Education (Learning) for Year 6 Standard Content 1.7 - Aquatic: Swimming Technique. Each document of curriculum and assessment for each year in special education has a title related to aquatic or basic swimming. The researcher also analyzes some other documents including books and journals on Halliwick model. All of these documents were analyzed to form fractions found in the Aquaexplorers module. The arrangement in the module is formed according to the format of the daily teaching plan of teachers with interaction, focus, objectives, activities and records / teaching aids included. The arrangement of this module is obtained through expert recommendations and is designed to facilitate the teacher in using it.

Expert Recommendation Method (Poncette et al., 2020) is conducted by researchers by talking via email, Google Meet app and phone calls (Poncette et al., 2020). Researchers form modules and send modules to four appointed experts for them to see and provide feedback. Feedback is recovered through the Google Meet application, phone calls and written formulation sent via email. Each part is carefully formed to meet the needs of students based on the analysis of the Physical Education curriculum and assessment documents and adopted by special education integration teachers. The implementation of each session is done in detail and explained carefully for each session.

Interaction one started with the mental adjustment which was the first point in the Halliwick model. In this point, pupils will sit on the poolside and soak their feet, patting the water followed by the movement of swivel entry. This adjustment's mental is very important to provide students the idea on what they will face further in this module and adapt them to pass through it. The movement of the water while they soak their feet before entering the water is the progressing steps that helps pupils adapt to the environment.

Next step is the Bobbing & Bubbling activity, which is a respiratory activity with the counting series of 1,3,5,7,9 repetition. Bobbing & Bubbling is a respiratory training activity which is a very crucial skills because breathing is the most important skill in water activities.

Without respiratory skills, students will be easily panicked, scared and prior to drown if they put the face in the water. The repetition of one, three, five and so on is to train pupils to do this activity in the right way as well as sharpening their counting skills that are important for learning. The last activity is a small game named "Blow Ball". Through previous activities, Bobbing & Bubbling, teachers will be able to identify students who are afraid to put the face in the water and fear with splashes of water to the face. This game requires students to blow ping-pong balls on the surface of the water that will familiarize these pupils with the splashes in the face. Through this game, the difficulties of students to do Bobbing & Bubbling activities can be overcome.

Interaction two in this module is initiated with float activity which is prone floating. This activity is an adaptation of points 2 to 5 in Halliwick Method. This point is very important to enhance posture control in water by applying the easy way in points 2 to 5 in Halliwick Method which is self-inflicted skills and control movements either vertically, deflecting, stretching and moving in positions published from this position. In order to apply it, the students only need to hold their breath, submerge their face in the water and make sure the body is relaxed from using any muscle. Self-confidence is very important in this point for them to be convinced that they will not drown and will immerse safely on the surface of the water if they follow the instructions carefully and it also includes point 6 in Halliwick Method.

Interaction three are initiated by the second floating skills which is supine floating. This skill adapts points 2 to 7 in Halliwick Method where the ability to control the body while floating to be stable on water and control the body to make rotation on the surface of the water is practiced. The applied techniques are to immerse on the surface of the water with the help of teachers, respiratory control and relaxation of the body. This session is continued with a small game named "Choose Colour". In this game, students will be able to learn to identify colours while playing and feeling a healthy competition experience with friends. The inhibited elements of this activity will ensure that the students learns basic knowledge that is identifying the colour while rejoicing in the water.

The fourth interaction are initiated with a fairly challenging activity which is Push & Glide, Regain Feet. This activity is an adaptation of point 8 in the Halliwick Method, the turbulent gliding. In this skill, it is important for students to integrate skills and execute the movement smoothly so that there is no undesirable movement such as staggering and sinking. Students will slide by kicking the wall and moving towards the teacher waiting in the middle of the pool. Students can stand by applying regain feet skills after the slide stops, sliding slightly or when they arrive to the teacher. Next is a small game activity named "Treasure Hunt". In this game, students will be able to build confidence, courage as well as enjoying diving to the pool floor. While at the bottom of the pool, students will grab a sinking toys and players with the most toys will be counted as winners.

The fifth interactions started with a quite complex movement and end with a high level skills. Small game derived from a real netball game will also be implemented. This interaction begins with the movement of hands adapting points 9 and 10 in Halliwick Method. The hand movement is the correct way to do the hand action for frontcrawl swimming style. Mini netball game is a very suitable game as exposure to real netball games with just basic rules applied in this game. Special Education Integration Program (PPKI) can also experience fun in socializing, communicating, collaborating while training the skills of the hands-on movement which is very important in the foundation of the aquatic skills. Hand movement in throwing the

ball during the game will be able to train the strength of hands and hand control which is also the basis for swimming skills.

3. Methodology

This pilot study are conducted by applying the Aquaexplorers module: Water Activity Guide for Integration Special Education Teachers to 17 Integration Special Education Teachers from 17 PPKIs in Penang State through 3 sessions within three days of the course. This module construction and development has been reviewed and confirmed by four experts which are the Excellent Lecturer of Physical Education, Special Education Lecturer, Certified Trainer Swimming for Special Needs from Malaysia Swimming Teacher Association and Excellent Special Education Teacher in Penang (Ikart, 2019).

The assessment instrument used in this pilot study is a questionnaire. To date, researchers often refer experts who have the theory of knowledge or practical experience in building a questionnaire to study the questionnaire and criticize the questionnaire built as a technical tracking technique in the questionnaire, the risk of mistakes in measurements or events in the process of answering questions (Olson, 2010). Expert Overview is a common practice in the development of the questionnaire (Yan et al. 2012) and it can be done by asking the expert to check and comment on the questionnaire (Willis et al., 1999) or by using a group of experts called as Expert Panel to study the questionnaire (DeMaio & Landreth, 2003). Producing a perfect questionnaire is impossible, but what is important is that the questionnaire responded to the objectives and questions of the study (Ikart, 2019). The study by Ikart (2019) has used a four-member survey method to review and comment on the questionnaire on education and vocational training to prisoners in Australia. This technique is also adopted in the formation of the questionnaire of this study where four experts in the field (Ikart, 2019) are the Excellent Lecturer of Physical Education, Special Education Lecturer, Certified Trainer Swimming for Special Needs from Malaysia Swimming Teacher Association and Excellent Special Education Teacher in Penang are appointed as reviewers in the construction of questions in this survey. The researcher has built a questionnaire to answer every objective and question of research and researchers has been using expert survey methods (Ikart, 2019) as a process of development and improvement of questionnaires.

3.1 The Instrument Validation Process

The instruments in this study consists of two section which is the first section consists of questions regarding the teachers knowledge on handling water activities and the second sections consist of questions on the teacher's self confidence in handling water activities for special needs students (learning disability).After getting a specialist assessment feedback for the validity of the instrument content, the researcher used the Cohen Kappa Correlation Analysis technique for the validity value of this instrument (Othman & Kassim, 2018). The results of the assessment of four experts show Expert 1 and Expert 3 agree with all 12 questions in the questionnaire. However, experts 2 disagree with one question and expert 4 disagree with eight questions in the questionnaire. Therefore, Cohen Kappa's analysis is conducted to assess the correlation between Expert 2 and Expert 4 as Cohen Kappa's data analysis can be used to assess the correlation between two experts who are seen to have discrepancies or disagreement (Othman & Kassim, 2018). The results of Cohen Kappa's

analysis between the two experts show Cohen Kappa 0.460 value and according to Landis and Koch (1977), this value is considered moderate while according to Cicchetti et al (1985) as well as Fleiss and Cohen (1973), this value is considered good.

3.2 The Protocol and Procedures

Upon completion of the construction and verification process, the questionnaire was given by researchers to 17 special educational teachers Integration before and after the implementation of the Aquaexplorers module and the results of questionnaire were tested using the Chi Square method in the Statistical Package For The Social Science (SPSS) software because of this questionnaire using a linear scale value of one to five (Simamora, 2017; Jetsu, 2020).

The administration of the study began with researchers applying for approval from Universiti Sains Malaysia and the Ministry of Education Malaysia before conducting this study. The research procedures and instruments have been presented to all related parties including the Head of Special Education Unit, Penang State Education Department and the teachers in Special Education Integrated Schools involved. The study procedure was described to the samples which are 17 special education teachers in Penang before the pilot study.

Pre-test data collection sessions will be conducted before the intervention sessions of using the AquaExplorers module: Water Activity Guide for Special Integration Education Teachers and post-data collection sessions will be conducted after completion of intervention using AquaExplorers module: Water Activity Guide for Special Integration Education Teachers. The questionnaire will be provided in the form of Google form and can be reached by the samples through the QR code scan that will be provided at the course registration desk. The course will be conducted at the Swimming Pool of Universiti Sains Malaysia for three days as the first day for introduction, basic swimming skills test, and also a bit of module implementation, second day of full module implementation and third day is a practical session with Special Education (Learning Disability) students.

The researcher will make an explanation on the details of the study to the samples (n: 17) before starting the intervention session. Protocols in carrying out interventions involving movement skills require verbal instructions, demonstrations and demonstrations accompanied by treatment attempts (Staples & Reid, 2010). The demonstration from the researcher will be repeated if the samples of the study cannot understand and follow the activity in the intervention. Demonstrations and instructions will be given repeatedly according to the understanding of the sample to ensure that all samples understand with the instructions given as the majority of samples have no basis in swimming skills (Roid & Miller, 1997).

AquaExplorers module: Water Activity Guide for Special Education Teachers Integration has been modified so that it is appropriate to be applied to various categories of Special Education (Learning Disability) students in the comprehensive educational program as a whole and the sample of the study can carry out activities with the best performance and capabilities that exist in themselves. Special Education Teachers Integration involved with this study is not a sports teacher or teacher who has a solid foundation in managing water activities or doing water activities but their essential duties require them to carry out this activity without any exposure. The administration and protocol of this study have been established to facilitate the samples through intervention and collection of data as well as the benefit of the study.

The question of research is formed through data collected from the Penang State Education Department and the results of the past study. In collaboration with the Special Education Unit, Penang State Education Department, and a hypothesis has been created which is there are no significance difference in the Special Education Integration Teacher's knowledge and confidence level in handling water activities for Special Education (Learning Disability) students after the implementation of this Aquaexplorers Modules. This study will test this hypothesis.

4. Result and Conclusion

Questionnaire answered by 17 Special Education Integration Teachers was analyzed using the Chi Square method of SPSS software. Questionnaire answers were compared to identify the questionnaire scores before and after intervention. The results of comparisons between these two tests showed the results of the data analysis of the post-test questionnaire ($m = 46.11$, $SD = 3.230$) were higher than the results of the pre-test questionnaire analysis ($m = 33.11$, $sd = 2.208$). The findings of this analysis show that the results of the post-questionnaire are better and this proves that the use of the Aquaexplorers module in this pilot test is indeed capable of improving the knowledge and self-confidence of Special Education Integration Teachers in carrying out the water activities.

The findings also show that all samples agreed that using a guided modules really helps them in conducting water activities. However, the samples also suggest few improvements that can be done in implementing this modules which is adjust the course to be longer (17.6%), adding activity for self-confidence in water (11.8%), adding demonstration video links in the module (11.8%), added repetition of important activity (5.9%), added more samples for each school (5.9%), and expand this course to other states (5.9%). All the proposed improvements that have been given in the post-questionnaire by the sample of this study have been accounted for and are included in the development of the module. The new module will be applied with all the proposed improvements where self-confidence activities in water have been added for all 10 new module interaction sessions, each skill has also been equipped with demonstration video and links using QR code and repetition of activities is also placed in every interaction for important skills. Based on a pilot study, researchers realize that Bobbing & Bubbling sessions need to be repeated in each session for mental Adjustment (MA) according to the Halliwick module. This is because Bobbing & Bubbling is a very important skill to control the breath in the water and most samples cannot make and remember the skills only with one session. For the proposed addition of activities, the improvements that need to be done in this module are the addition of activities from various levels and difficulty levels. Various activities with different difficulty levels can meet the needs of samples consisting of various categories and levels of ability. Classroom Outdoor Learning (PLBD) Module 3 will usually take whole day to be carried out as activities will be carried out at the convenience of the school and requires a neat setup, then by increasing the number of activities at each session, PLBD can be carried out with optimal and effective use of time. For the idea of addition of samples and expansion to other states, the idea has been proposed to the Penang State Education Department.

5. Discussions and Recommendations

The modules with the activities placed as an introduction, the main objective as well as small games as a closure can make the module become more practical and user-friendly for the teacher. Researchers also suggest that activities on each interaction are added and divided properly as the lesson plan so it can be more practical to be used by the teacher.

The addition of small games in every activity is also a smart move. By adding a small game at the end of each session, researchers realize that the communication and social skills of these students have increased from day to day. They learn to communicate, cooperate and can also socialize to win the game. Researchers also recommend that based on their observations, more aspects can be reviewed based on the use of this module as the enhancement of student communication and social skills throughout the study.

Based on the observation of the researcher during the pilot test, the statement or the description of the points from Halliwick module in the module also does not bring any benefit to the teacher and sometimes merely mislead them. Thus, the researcher carried out the Halliwick point statement from the module and which means the point is not stated but it has been elaborated into Aquaexplorers point.

Future researcher can improve the Aquaexplorers Module by adding the improvements suggestions by the research samples which are adjust the course to be longer, adding activity for self-confidence in water, adding demonstration video links in the module, added repetition of important activity, added more samples from each school, and expand this course to other states. The researcher hope that all the recommendations given by the samples can be used in improving this modules into a better one.

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